

THE EFFECTS OF GLOBALIZATION ON HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Purpose *In the current world that we are living, events and changes follow one another with astonishing rapidity, and as far as the business world is concerned, these rapid changes are beginning to become part of the normal activity of companies. In this situation, the human resources need to show multiple professional skills, creativity and ability to adapt to different changes.*

Methodology/approach *In the current context of multiple changes, people are a vital resource, able to ensure the survival, development and success of the organizations they belong to. In these conditions, it is absolutely natural for organizations to be more and more concerned with selecting the most competent candidates, "the right people in the right place", even if the costs of recruitment and selection are not negligible, especially if these processes are organized by specialized companies. The paper aims to conduct a study on the methods applied by staff recruitment companies in the current context of globalization.*

Findings *The study was conducted at a staff recruitment and selection company, whose field of activity extend to three essential aspects in terms of human resources, namely: staff recruitment, staff leasing and professional evaluation projects.*

Research limitations/implications *The proposed research method of human resource selection, to meet the requirements and wishes of any manager, ensuring the expected results both for him/her and the selected staff, starting from the current context of the economy.*

Practical implications *Over the time, but especially during this period, there are essential changes that raise a number of problems related to the world economy, which has led to an explosive rise in unemployment, but also a number of problems related to technological changes, an uncontrolled rise in inflation, budgetary problems. The liberalization of the international financial circuit has led to an intensification of international trade. Over time, multi-national companies have taken a representative place in the progress of the global economy. This aspect has been and is being studied by various specialists who have stated that their existence brings positive aspects to the global economy.*

Originality/value *Over the time, organizations are developing and dealing more and more with a number of key aspects in human resource management. Managers are increasingly aware of the importance of creating a plan to attract and retain for as long as possible people who have the skills the organization needs. The implementation of that involves both the recruitment, selection, integration, training of candidates/ employees, but also their reward choosing the most appropriate and attractive benefits at the same time. A fair and motivating reward system for employees also involves the implementation of a plan for periodic evaluations of their performance, performance that is also reflected in achieving organizational objectives. The purpose of this paper is to study the ways that organizations can apply in streamlining the selection, selection and improvement of the workforce in the current context.*

Key words: *human resources, globalization, recruitment, organization.*

Introduction

In the last years, there has been an increase in international competition, as a result of the amplification of the globalization process. Globalization is a moment in the process of globalization, whose main

actors are companies, especially multinationals (Bică and Constantinescu, 2007). Most authors consider that multinational corporations are companies that have expanded their production and marketing activities beyond the borders of the countries where they were established (Constantinescu-Băeșu, 2006).

A defining feature of the multinational company is the expansion of economic and financial activity outside the country where the company was established, resulting in a vast international scale composed of a parent company, called the parent company and a variable number of subsidiaries, opened in various countries and who are in a dependent relationship with the parent company (Albescu, 2012).

Besides the social, political and economic effects, globalization has also impacted the field of human resources and in the context of intensified competition between multinational corporations, the role of human resources management cannot be ignored, it is in fact one of the most important factors which ensures success (Ștefan and Roman, 2012).

Traditionally, human resources management has a dual purpose, namely, to integrate social objectives into the general objectives of the enterprise as well as to coordinate the different aspects of the actual management of human resources (Lefter et al., 2008). Despite that, under the influence of globalization, companies become the actors of a competitive framework with an increasingly strong and wide international tone where company managers are forced to rethink the role that human resources departments have, giving special importance to the following factors:

- the ability to react on a highly competitive market, within the global business structures;
- close connections with the company's strategic plans;
- involvement of both managers and employees in the definition and implementation of objectives;
- orientation towards quality, productivity, teamwork and workforce flexibility (Ștefan and Roman, 2012).

As a result, companies in various fields of activity have intensified their efforts in identifying and continuously training their employees. Companies around the world are working hard to keep up with the competition. Human resources are an important factor, which ensure the continuity and continuous development of the company's activity.

The emergence and development of the globalization process brings advantages and disadvantages. Certainly, one of the advantages is attracting the capital needed for growth and development as well as much more new developed technology that cannot be generated locally. Another positive aspect would be the managerial experience and the substantial development of jobs which entails revenues to the state budget. Among the negative effects, we can mention the fact that the opening to the worldwide markets attracts quickly also all the external negative effects.

The registration and development of multinational companies on the Romanian market has had over the time an upward evolution, that can be seen in the data published by the Romanian National Institute of Statistics, press, 2017 – figure 1 and figure 2.

Companies around the world are aware that they have to face stiff competition in order to survive. In many cases, when expanding into a foreign country, multinational companies choose to send their managers and specialists to focus on opening branches specific to the parent company but prefer to recruit their employees from the local workforce.

Manolescu (2004) said in a paper that “managerial styles at the level of different multinational companies have proven their efficiency and effectiveness internally but most of the time externally they have led to frustrations and achievements below the expected level. That is why in order to ensure its international success, a company must take into account not only the financial and marketing considerations according to which many of the decisions are made, but especially the aspects related to the labor force”.

Figure 1: Distribution of the number of enterprise groups by CAEN Rev.2 activities sections and types of groups (Romanian National Institute of Statistics, press, 2017)

Figure 2: Structure of enterprise subgroups in Romania, by share of number of employees (%) (Romanian National Institute of Statistics, press, 2017)

The labor force is the one that ensures the survival development and success of a company on the market. Insurance costs and labor development are rising for companies but this investment in people is considered the safest way to ensure the company's survival and development. The active human resources of the organization are able to reproduce and develop the other resources necessary for a company to increase its efficiency and effectiveness.

Managerial decisions in the field of human resources are difficult and must be very responsible. Each employee must be treated differently, depending on past activities taking into account also what is expected of them in the future.

Inside and outside the company, staff training can be achieved through very diverse methods and techniques. To ensure their effectiveness it is preferable that they be integrated into the general policy of the company and be followed by an analysis of job openings and the evaluation of people.

A Case Study in staff recruitment

The case study was conducted at a consulting company in the field of human resources with considerable experience in the market. The company is part of a group with 100% Romanian capital being formed by a consulting and a training company.

As an area of expertise, the company focuses in three directions: namely personnel recruitment, personnel leasing and professional evaluation with the main purpose of offering consulting. In order to achieve this goal, it has at its disposal an important number of HR consultants with backgrounds in different fields of activity which contribute to an improvement of the services offered in accordance with the feedback received from the client and the candidates.

The responsibilities of the company's employees are similar, in other words all team members deal with the research part related to open positions and client companies, the sourcing part, strategy preparation, maintaining contact with clients and candidates throughout the entire recruitment process and recruitment part, interviews reports and statuses.

The management of the company is a well-organized having established certain rules regarding the behavioral, physical and technical part. The approach of inactive clients on the labor market supposes keeping up to date the information regarding the actuality of the job.

The services offered by the company are varied and are aimed at recruitment, selection, assessment and consulting. The recruitment and selection part involve a strategy that follows the direct search, networking, use of the database available at the company level, candidates file, but also recruitment online or through advertisements.

This direct search refers to an identification of candidates who are not active in their search for a job. Networking is another essential method that aims to help transform local projects in national or even international projects. Its main purpose is to form relationships with other people and to maintain them over time in order to stimulate the evolution of the business.

Considering the current context and the continuous development of the globalization process, we can say that an intense activity can be observed within the professional networks which can increase the visibility in the professional area of activity.

Change in the Number of Job Advertisements^a

^a In the period from March–May 2019 to March–May 2020, measured as a proportion of all job ads on LinkedIn. Source: LinkedIn 2020; calculations by the ifo Institute.

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Figure 3: Change in the number of job advertisements (IFO institute, press, 2020)

The chart in figure 3 presented by the Info Institute shows a substantial increase in published posts in the field of health and software and a serious reduction in those in other fields, a situation due to the problems facing humanity globally.

Recruiting candidates online involves an active search through various specialized recruitment sites but does not exclude situations in which the company publishes ads for open positions, a context in which there are a number of candidates eager to make a career change or to find a new job.

A way of assessing the development needs and highlighting leadership, coordination and communication skills is done through the assessment center. In the case of companies that want to recruit specialized personnel in certain field of activity a contract is made between the client company and the recruitment company.

Although recruitment seems a relatively simple situation organizing the process at the level of recruitment companies is quite complex. The staff of the companies is organized in teams led by a project manager who has the role of ensuring that the wishes of the clients are satisfied at the highest level. The process is a very complex one materializing in regular information meetings with the client. During the first discussion with the client, the work strategy is elaborated, and all the details are gathered, while the client is making available to the team all the information considered relevant in order to be able to make the most appropriate and responsible choice relative to client's needs. The involvement of the client is particularly important because the entire recruitment process is done in agreement with him. The meeting ends by setting a deadline.

The next step is to inform the client about:

- the context of the job opening;
- requirements and responsibilities;
- the level of experience required;
- foreign languages that must be known by the candidates;
- the tests that may or may not be applied in the selection process;
- the requested recommendations
- the start date of the recruitment;
- the allocated budget;
- the strategy that will be followed by the team to achieve the goal.

In order to avoid stagnation, the applied strategy must be designed in such a way to cover a wide range of candidates as possible. The way of promoting the open position is essential since it needs to attract the interest of as many applicants as possible, therefore it must be both specific and attractive.

Determining how to contact candidates is another key aspect. The approach must be friendly, and the information must be short and to the point if we are talking about entry level roles or in the IT industry. It is essential that the approach be personalized but also equally attractive.

How to conduct the selection interview is another important aspect. The success of an interview depends to a large extent on the skills and experience of the interviewer, who needs to know how to start the discussion, possibly through friendly discussion, ice-breaking discussions. This preliminary phase of the interview is followed by discussions on how the candidate understood the requirements and responsibilities of the position in question. A good interviewer knows how to communicate with a candidate, providing him/her with additional information about the company and the position for which he/she applied and obtaining from him/her all the information needed in order to ensure that the best candidate for the job is selected. The presentation of the client company needs to be as attractive as possible to the candidate and as well as the presentation of the position the candidate applied for. A consultant who presents some information mechanically and rigidly will not be able to make an attractive presentation for the candidate. Also, at this stage the aspects relating to the holding of possible technical tests are discussed. The interview ends with discussions regarding the notice period and financial expectations. Completion of the recruitment process involves reporting all the data to the team manager who will inform the client. Even after the completion of the process and the hiring of the candidate the recruitment company will keep in touch with the candidate to find out if he/she is satisfied with the new job.

The analyzed recruitment company is a long-standing company which stands out through:

- a good organization of the activity with a set rules established and in place;
- it has diversified projects that allow employees a way of professional development with positive effects in reducing recruitment time;
- open way of working through discussions with both: clients and candidates;
- development plan for consultants.

But there are also weak points that the company makes every effort to correct like: a system that does not allow the centralization of data to achieve a simplified workflow, IT equipment that needs updating and a small number of consultants. All these issues are being taken care by the management.

Conclusions

In conclusion we note that the company analyzed in the case study is a mediator between client and candidates, this requires careful documentation of consultants on the history, products and processes of the client, on the vision, mission and values promoted which need to correspond to those of the candidates, that the company will recruit for the client. Candidates are identified not only by classical methods but also by an active search. This approach aims to increase the pool of potential candidates suitable for the job recruited and thus streamline the recruitment process.

A first positive aspect that we recall is the fact that the company's management is very well organized which ensures good communication and effective feedback between manager and employees, a very important aspect for the success of any company but also for employee satisfaction. The good development of the company activity also implies and the existence of clear procedures and rules regarding the behavioral, physical and technical part of the organization. A plus for the company is the fact that these consultants have backgrounds in various field of activity thus being more versatile, ready to respond to requests from customers who each consider different profiles of candidates depending on the domain of activity.

As in any company here are aspects that can be improved and that once optimized can increase the quality and efficiency of the recruitment process. Among the aspects that need to be remedied we mention: the improvement of the IT system, the acquisition of new and high-performance equipment that will make consultants' work more efficient and easier, internal trainings, brainstorming sessions.

We believe that the involvement of consultants in the process of improving or reviewing applicable procedures may also be recommended as the information they provide may be valuable. This involvement would also give employees a sense of professional satisfaction and deepen their loyalty relationship with the company. We also consider that it would be a good thing to implement/improve a feedback system from the clients they serve but also from the candidates' subject to recruitment.

A famous quote from Richard Branson says: "Clients do not come first. Employees come first. If you care of your employees, they will take care of your clients."

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